

SWOT Adopt a Crossover Field Campaign—Cape Hatteras (MAB-SWOT)
Current and Pressure Sensor Equipped Inverted Echo Sounder (CPIES) Technical Report
Descriptions of the L0-L2 CPIES Data

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Notes:

28 June 2024a: The first version of this report does not yet include data from P3 and P6. This report and the accompanying published datasets will be updated once those records are available (anticipated March 2025).

28 June 2024b: L3 and L4 datasets and derived products are beyond the scope of this technical report and will be reported elsewhere.

26 June 2025: The second version of this report includes data from P3 (P6 was not recovered). This version also includes corrections resulting corrected IES Clock Drifts. The processing code to create the L2 dataset will be made available upon request from the authors.

Citation:

Version 2 (this version):

Wang, Y. D., & Andres, M. (2025). SWOT Adopt a Crossover Field Campaign—Cape Hatteras (MAB-SWOT) Current and Pressure Sensor Equipped Inverted Echo Sounder (CPIES) Technical Report (Version 2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16851887>.

All versions:

Wang, Ysabel D., M. Andres, 2024. SWOT Adopt a Crossover Field Campaign—Cape Hatteras (MAB-SWOT) Current and Pressure Sensor Equipped Inverted Echo Sounder (CPIES) Technical Report, Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution, Technical Report, doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12583848.

Version 1: doi:10.5281/zenodo.12583849; Published June 28, 2024.

Version 2: doi:10.5281/zenodo.16851887; Published August 13, 2025.

Last updated August 8, 2025.

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1. Introduction

Measurements from six current and pressure sensor equipped inverted echo sounders (CPIESs) were collected along and offshore of the Middle Atlantic Bight (MAB) near Cape Hatteras, NC, USA for an 18-month period (January 2023-June 2024) as part of the broader **SWOT Adopt a Crossover Field Campaign—Cape Hatteras (MAB-SWOT)** project (Figure 1 and Table 1). This is a project funded by JPL/NASA with a contract to the University of North Carolina Chapel Hill (UNC) and with subcontracts to the Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution (WHOI) and Coastal Studies Institute/East Carolina University (CSI). The lead PI is Harvey Seim (UNC) and co-PIs are Robert Todd and Magdalena Andres (WHOI), and Mike Muglia (CSI). The project is endorsed by and falls under the umbrella of the Surface Water Ocean Topography (SWOT) Adopt a Crossover Consortium: <https://www.swot-adac.org/>. The MAB-SWOT project has “adopted” the SWOT crossover site that falls east of Cape Hatteras: <https://www.swot-adac.org/campaigns/mab-swot/>.

This technical report describes data from the CPIES-component of the project. The six CPIES were deployed from the *R/V Neil Armstrong* on cruise AR71 in January 2023. Four of the CPIESs were recovered from *R/V Roger Revelle* on cruise RR2407 in June 2024 and one CPIES was recovered from *R/V Neil Armstrong* on a transit cruise, AR86-07, in March 2025. The remaining instrument (P6) was not recovered. As of this writing, the technical report here describes the Level 0-2 CPIES datasets and the associated processing of these 5 instruments (Wang and Andres, 2025).

Table 1. CPIES coordinates and average bottom water depth

Inst. Site	Latitude (°N)	Longitude (°W)	Avg. water depth (m)*
P1	36.2334	74.3662	2026.3
P2	35.9997	74.5339	1854.3
P3	36.0039	74.1969	2531.8
P4	36.0001	74.6728	1219.4
P5	36.0001	74.3671	2152.1
P6	35.7502	74.2832	

*Average depths calculated from the time-average pressure records with atmospheric pressure (10.13 dbar) subtracted. P6 was nominally located at 2403 m based on multibeam measurements taken during deployment.

Figure 1. Bathymetry map showing locations of the CPIESs recovered in June 2024 (yellow). P3 was recovered in March 2025 and P6 (red) was not recovered.

2. CPIES Data Records

2.1 CPIES Sensors and Settings

CPIESs provide measures of bottom pressure, bottom temperature, round-trip surface-to-bottom acoustic travel time (τ) and horizontal velocities and temperature 50 m above the seabed. The CPIESs' PAROS pressure sensors were each model 46k and the current sensors were Aanderaa Zpulse 4930R.

Each of the CPIESs was set to the following sampling schedule (see also the .txt files in the L0/Mission_setups):

- Travel time measurements: 16 pings every 10 minutes ('fast τ ' mode).
- Bottom pressure and temperature measured every 10 minutes.
- Near-bottom velocity (u,v) and temperature measurement every 10 minutes.

The records from the 5 recovered CPIESs are essentially complete, except for the travel time measurement at P4.

2.2 Description of the Data Levels

Level 0 (L0): *raw data from the platform, often in format from the manufacturer. Retained as the most fundamental form of the observations but often not used in analysis.* For CPIESs, these are the .dat files saved as raw output by the instrument. See the Inverted Echo Sounder User's Manual IES Model 6.2C (Section 4 DATA RECOVERY and ANALYSIS – 4.2.1 File Types) for further details on the data formats. Also included are the .txt files automatically saved at instrument deployment by the computer used for mission set up.

Level 1 (L1): *initially-processed data, retaining the original sampling scheme (in time-space).* For CPIESs, these are the data from the instruments converted from .dat format to .mat format (using IES_GUIDAT2MAT), and include the raw ping data (96 per hour) for round trip acoustic travel time. See the Appendix (section A.1) for plots and see the Inverted Echo Sounder User's Manual IES Model 6.2C (Section 4 DATA RECOVERY and ANALYSIS – 4.2.1 File Types) for further details on the data formats.

Level 2 (L2): *similar to L1 but with further QC, and processing, and some calibrations applied.* For CPIESs, there are three components of L2 data: (1) hourly data records, (2) low pass filtered data records, and (3) the amplitude and phase of the barotropic tides calculated using the Response Method (Munk and Cartwright, 1966). The processing is done with the University of Rhode Island (URI) codes using IES_GUIDRIVER. This step includes despiking acoustic travel time and temperature records, and identifying and removing any pressure-sensor drifts prior to tidal analysis of pressures. Currents are measured relative to magnetic north not True North, so a correction is applied here to account for local magnetic declination. L2 data files are appended to include each CPIES site's (1) magnetic declination, (2) latitude, (3) longitude and (4) average depth (calculated from the time-mean pressure record converted to depth). In addition, the measured u and v are renamed $u_uncorrected$ and $v_uncorrected$ and the magnetic declination is applied to correct the velocities (u, v). See the Appendix (section A.2) for plots and the Inverted Echo Sounder Data Processing Manual (Kennelly et al., 2022) for a description of the processing tools and file naming convention.

Versions (v#): As updates and processing corrections are applied, different versions of the L2 data may be produced. Presently, *there are two versions of the L2 corrected and uncorrected data. Version 2 is an update to version 1 that includes (1) the data from P3 (which was recovered after version 1 was published) and (2) a correction to the IES CLOCK DRIFT. The values should have*

been negative (IES time lagging clock time), but were inadvertently entered as positive in version 1. This has little effect on the 2-day lowpass filtered records, but it does slightly influence the hourly records and therefore the calculation of the barotropic tide and the internal tide signal.

2.3. CPIES Data Processing Procedure

L0 .DAT files (in folders with naming convention: P##_SN### having ## site number and ### CPIES serial number) collected from the instrument are converted to L1 .MAT files using IES_GUIDAT2MAT. The resulting L1 .MAT files are then processed further using IES_GUIDRIVER with instrument-specific settings, such as Clock Drift and Time Offset. This processing step accounts for despiking and removal of sensor drift and identification of the barotropic tide signal in the pressure record. A sample of the settings and parameters used to process the P5 CPIES is shown in **Figure 2** with analogous settings used for the other instruments.

The output of IES_GUIDRIVER is further corrected by rotating velocities to account for magnetic declination (Section 2.4.4.1). The final L2 files have each instrument’s latitude, longitude, magnetic declination angle, and average depth appended to them. Processed L2 files with hourly data are saved under the filenames P#.mat. Two-day low-pass filtered L2 records, also outputted by IES_GUIDRIVER, are saved as a separate file under the filenames P#lp.mat with the records subsampled to 0.5 day intervals. The 2-day low pass filtered L2 records also include the amplitudes and phases of the barotropic tides for 8 tidal constituents (see **Table 3**).

The most recent version of the IES processing code, IESpkg4p06, calculates a tidal component of each hourly acoustic travel time record that arises due to pathlength changes as the barotropic tide raises and lowers the sea surface (“tau_tide”), and subtracts this from the full hourly acoustic travel time record. However, since this code uses a fixed sea water sound speed (1500 m/s), this calculation may not be accurate enough for studies of internal tides. Hence, in the data records presented here, this has been added back to the travel time record and the “tidal_tau” variable has been discarded. The barotropic tidal contribution to hourly tau records will be identified and reported in the L3 data sets, along with the baroclinic tidal contributions to tau.

Table 2. CPIES deployment and recovery information.

Instrument Site	CPIES SN	Deployment Time			Time Offset (min)	Clock Drift ¹ (min)
		Date	(GMT)	Local (EST)		
P1	283	20230105	11:43	6:43	0	-1.6
P2	304	20230105	18:43	13:43	0	-1.32
P3	305	20230106	2:24	21:24 (01/05)	0	-2.40
P4	321	20230105	16:04	11:04	0	-0.83
P5	332	20230105	23:28	18:28	0	-2.70
P6	446	20230106	8:31	3:31		

¹Negative Clock Drift indicates that IES clock lags real time.

Table 3. Amplitudes and phases associated with the barotropic tidal constituents at each CPIES location determined by the Response Method (Munk and Cartwright, 1966) and dedrifted pressure records.

Tidal Constituent		Site ID				
		P1	P2	P3	P4	P5
O1	Amplitude (dbar)	0.0706	0.0709	0.0707	0.0711	0.0708
	Phase (°)	186.008	186.542	186.312	186.653	186.491
K1	Amplitude (dbar)	0.0917	0.0916	0.0914	0.0916	0.0914
	Phase (°)	181.356	181.736	181.640	182.180	181.797
Q1	Amplitude (dbar)	0.0155	0.0155	0.0155	0.0157	0.0155
	Phase (°)	183.544	183.720	184.514	184.020	184.366
P1	Amplitude (dbar)	0.0301	0.0301	0.0301	0.0301	0.0301
	Phase (°)	182.142	182.586	182.349	182.974	182.549
M2	Amplitude (dbar)	0.4301	0.4273	0.4288	0.4272	0.4290
	Phase (°)	352.352	352.476	352.667	352.739	352.558
K2	Amplitude (dbar)	0.0193	0.0191	0.0192	0.0191	0.0192
	Phase (°)	21.638	21.949	22.070	21.933	21.786
N2	Amplitude (dbar)	0.0984	0.0979	0.0978	0.0979	0.0979
	Phase (°)	335.3260	335.364	335.136	335.655	335.390
S2	Amplitude (dbar)	0.0833	0.0824	0.0832	0.0824	0.083
	Phase (°)	19.375	19.658	19.836	19.707	19.532

Figure 2. Sample settings and parameters used to process the CPIES (P5) using IES_GUIDRIVER.

2.4. CPIES L2 Processed Data: Definitions and Units

This section contains the descriptions (Table 4 and Table 5) and plots of L2 variables and a brief explanation of the corrections performed to account for magnetic declination.

Table 4. Hourly records (P#.mat)

Field name	Units	Description
amplitude	dbar	Tidal amplitudes of the barotropic tides at each CPIES site
cmtmp	°C	Hourly current meter temperature
cmtmpdd	days from 01/01/2023	Decimal day for cmtmp record
comments		Processing comments
dcs		Current meter serial number
dritt	dbar	Pressure sensor dritt
driftcoef		Coefficients for equation describing pressure sensor drift
paros		Pressure sensor serial number
phase	°	Tidal amplitudes of the barotropic tides at each CPIES site
prs	dbar	Hourly bottom pressure
prsave	dbar	Time-average bottom pressure
prsdd	days from 01/01/2023	Decimal day for prs record
refyr	year	Reference year
sn		CPIES serial number
tau	s	Hourly acoustic travel time (including the component due to the barotropic tide)
taudd	days from 01/01/2023	Decimal day for hourly tau record
tide	dbar	Hourly pressure signal due to barotropic tides
tmp	°C	Hourly PAROS sensor temperature record
tmpdd	days from 01/01/2023	Decimal day for hourly tmp record
magnetic_declination	°W	Magnetic declination*
u	cm/s	Hourly current meter eastward velocity with magnetic declination correction applied
v	cm/s	Hourly current meter north-south velocity with magnetic declination correction
u_uncorrected	cm/s	Hourly uncorrected current meter eastward velocity
v_uncorrected	cm/s	Hourly uncorrected current meter northward velocity
uvdd	days from 01/01/2023	Decimal days for u, v, u_uncorrected, v_uncorrected
depthave	m	Average bottom depth of CPIES**
lat	°N	CPIES latitude***
lon	°W	CPIES longitude***

*Magnetic declination is calculated with a mid-date of 09/22/2023 using the IGRF model from <https://www.ngdc.noaa.gov/geomag/calculators/magcalc.shtml>

**Average depths are calculated from average pressure with atmospheric pressure (10.13 dbar) subtracted.

***Calculated from the location at which the instrument was deployed at the sea surface with a drift estimated from the ocean currents as measured by the shipboard ADCP.

Table 5. Two-day low-pass filtered records subsampled at 0.5 day increments (P#lp.mat)

Field name	Units	Description
cmtmp	°C	Current meter temperature record
cmtmpdd	days from 01/01/2023	Decimal day for cmtmp
comments		Processing comments
dcs		Current meter serial number
paros		Pressure sensor serial number
prs	dbar	Bottom pressure record
prsave	dbar	Time-averaged bottom pressure
prsd	days from 01/01/2023	Decimal day for prs record
refyr	year	Reference year
sn		CPIES serial number
tau	s	Acoustic travel time record
taudd	days from 01/01/2023	Decimal day for acoustic travel time record
tmp	°C	PAROS sensor temperature record
tmpdd	days from 01/01/2023	Decimal date for tmp
magnetic_declination	°W	Magnetic declination*
u	cm/s	Current meter eastward velocity with magnetic declination correction
v	cm/s	Current meter northward velocity with magnetic declination correction
u_uncorrected	cm/s	Uncorrected current meter eastward velocity
v_uncorrected	cm/s	Uncorrected current meter northward velocity
uvdd	days from 01/01/2023	Decimal date for u, v, u_uncorrected, v_uncorrected
depthave	m	Average bottom depth of CPIES**
lat	°N	CPIES latitude***
lon	°W	CPIES longitude***

*Magnetic declination is calculated with a mid-date of 09/22/2023 using the IGRF model from <https://www.ngdc.noaa.gov/geomag/calculators/magcalc.shtml>

**Average depths are calculated from average pressure with atmospheric pressure (10.13 dbar) subtracted.

***Calculated from the location at which the instrument was deployed at the sea surface with a drift estimated from the ocean currents as measured by the shipboard ADCP.

2.4.1. Acoustic travel time records

Figure 3. Processed (L2) acoustic travel time records. Time series of hourly (blue) and 2-day low-pass filtered (orange). CPIES P4 did not record acoustic travel time.

2.4.2. Pressure records

2.4.2.1. Drifts and tides

Figure 4. Pressure drifts. Hourly pressure measurements, including the barotropic tides (blue) and the pressure variation due to pressure sensor drift plus the time-averaged pressure (orange). Note the longer deployment period for P3.

2.4.2.2. Dedrifting, detided records

Figure 5. Processed (L2) bottom pressure. Time series of hourly (blue) and 2-day low-pass filtered (orange).

2.4.3. Temperature records (from PAROS pressure sensor)

Figure 6. Bottom temperature records from the PAROS pressure sensor which is within the CPIES glass housing. Hourly temperature records (blue) and 2-day low-pass filtered (orange).

2.4.4. Current meter records

2.4.4.1. Corrections for magnetic declination

The CPIESs' L0 and L1 velocity records are referenced to local magnetic north; in the L2 records, these are corrected for their local magnetic declinations (**Table 6**) by rotating to True North. The original and uncorrected velocities in the L1 files (P#.u, P#.v, P#lp.u, P#lp.v) are retained in all L2 files and are renamed (P#.u_uncorrected, P#.v_uncorrected, P#lp.u_uncorrected, P#lp.v_uncorrected).

The magnetic declination of each CPIES is determined by each instrument's coordinates and is found in the IGRF23 model available via the [NOAA Magnetic Field Calculators](#). Magnetic declination varies temporally but is assumed to be uniform in time using the midpoint of the deployment (9/22/2023) as a reference date. Each L2 file contains this magnetic declination angle in degrees west (P#.magnetic_declination, P#lp.magnetic_declination).

Table 6. Magnetic declinations from IGRF23 used to correct u and v measured by the CPIESs' current sensors from L1 to L2 files. Reference dates for all four CPIES is 9/22/2023.

Instrument Site	CPIES SN	Latitude (°N)	Longitude (°W)	IGRF23 Magnetic Declination (°W)
P1	283	36.2333	74.3666	11.65
P2	304	35.9997	74.5339	11.54
P3	305	36.0069	74.1932	11.73
P4	321	36.0001	74.6728	11.47
P5	332	36.0012	74.3657	11.62
P6	446	35.7561	74.2781	11.62

2.4.4.2. Time varying L2 Currents

Figure 7. P1 current meter records. Top to bottom: Zonal (positive eastward) velocity, meridional (positive northward) velocity, stickplot, speed, and bottom temperature shown for the hourly (blue) and 2-day low-pass filtered (orange) records. Velocities have been corrected for magnetic declination.

Figure 8. P2 current meter records. Top to bottom: Zonal (positive eastward) velocity, meridional (positive northward) velocity, stickplot, speed, and bottom temperature shown for the hourly (blue) and 2-day low-pass filtered (orange) records. Velocities have been corrected for magnetic declination.

Figure 9. P3 current meter records. Top to bottom: Zonal (positive eastward) velocity, meridional (positive northward) velocity, stickplot, speed, and bottom temperature shown for the hourly (blue) and 2-day low-pass filtered (orange) records. Velocities have been corrected for magnetic declination.

Figure 10. P4 current meter records. Top to bottom: Zonal (positive eastward) velocity, meridional (positive northward) velocity, stickplot, speed, and bottom temperature shown for the hourly (blue) and 2-day low-pass filtered (orange) records. Velocities have been corrected for magnetic declination.

Figure 11. P5 current meter records. Top to bottom: Zonal (positive eastward) velocity, meridional (positive northward) velocity, stickplot, speed, and bottom temperature shown for the hourly (blue) and 2-day low-pass filtered (orange) records. Velocities have been corrected for magnetic declination.

3. References

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Appendix

A.1. CPIES L1 Data

This section contains figures of L1 processed pressure, acoustic travel time, and PAROS temperature records; engineering and DCS (current sensor) figures are not included here. These figures are generated automatically when the CPIES processing code IES_GUIDAT2MAT is run in Matlab.

A.1.1. P1 283

A.1.1.1. Pressure (PIES283_1_prs_1.png)

A.1.1.2. Acoustic travel time (PIES283_1_tau_1.png)

A.1.1.3. Temperature (PIES283_1_tmp_1.png)

A.1.2. P2 304

A.1.2.1. Pressure (PIES304_1_prs_1.png)

A.1.2.2. Acoustic travel time (PIES304_1_tau_1.png)

A.1.2.3. Temperature (PIES304_1_tmp_1.png)

A.1.3. P3 305

A.1.3.1. Pressure (PIES305_1_prs_1.png)

A.1.3.2. Acoustic travel time (PIES305_1_tau_1.png)

A.1.3.3. Temperature (PIES305_1_tmp_1.png)

A.1.4. P4 321

A.1.4.1. Pressure (PIES321_1_prs_1.png)

A.1.4.2. Acoustic travel time (PIES321_1_tau_1.png)

A.1.4.3. Temperature (PIES321_1_tmp_1.png)

A.1.5. P5 332

A.1.5.1. Pressure (PIES332_1_prs_1.png)

A.1.5.2. Acoustic travel time (PIES332_1_tau_1.png)

A.1.5.3. Temperature (PIES332_1_tmp_1.png)

A.2. CPIES L2 "First Look" Processed Data

This section contains figures of L2 processed records that are generated automatically when the CPIES processing code IES_GUIDRIVER is run in Matlab.

A.2.1. P1 283

A.2.1.1. P1 283 - Hourly Data

A.2.1.2. P1 283 - Pressure Data

A.2.1.3. P1 283 - 2-day Low-pass filtered data

A.2.2. P2 304

A.2.2.1. P2 304 - Hourly Data

A.2.2.2. P2 304 - Pressure Data

A.2.2.3. P2 304 - 2-day Low-pass filtered data

A.2.3. P3 305

A.2.3.1. P3 305 - Hourly Data

A.2.3.2. P3 305 - Pressure Data

A.2.3.3. P3 305 - 2-day Low-pass filtered data

A.2.4. P4 321

A.2.4.1. P4 321 - Hourly Data

A.2.4.2. P4 321 - Pressure Data

A.2.4.3. P4 321 - 2-day Low-pass filtered data

A.2.5. P5 332

A.2.5.1. P5 332 - Hourly Data

A.2.5.2. P5 332 - Pressure Data

A.2.5.3. P5 332 - 2-day Low-pass filtered data

